
Revisiting Crisis and Emergency Risk Communication (CERC) in Disaster Governance: Evidence from Indonesia

Yuswarni¹, Tobirin²

^{1,2}Public administration doctoral program, Faculty of Social and Political Science, Jenderal Soedirman University

ABSTRACT

This study aims to examine how Crisis and Emergency Risk Communication (CERC) is implemented in disaster management in Indonesia and identify the components that influence its performance. The CERC theory is used as an analytical framework in this study to understand the dynamics of communication in each phase of the crisis. The method used is a qualitative approach through a literature review, where various international journals, official reports, and policy documents related to crisis communication were collected, studied, and analyzed. The results show that institutions in Indonesia are not functioning optimally, characterized by weak inter-institutional coordination, inconsistent messages, delays in information, and low public trust. In addition, socio-cultural factors and limited access to technology also influence the distribution of information and data. The results of this study confirm that the effectiveness of communication in crisis situations is determined not only by the speed and accuracy of information, but also by the ability to build trust and adapt to new situations.

KEYWORDS: CERC, Disaster Governance, Risk Communication.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Disasters have become increasingly complex and systemic phenomena in the past two decades, no longer sporadic events. Environmental degradation, uncontrolled urbanization, and climate change have increased disasters worldwide, particularly in developing countries (Cutter, Burton, & Emrich, 2010), (Kelman, 2018), and (UNDRR, 2019). The current situation has shifted the paradigm of disaster management. A reactive approach has shifted to a proactive one, emphasizing preparedness, community adaptive capacity, and resilience (Tierney, 2019). Amid this shift, communication is often considered an additional component, despite its strategic role in determining the success of disaster management.

In disaster situations, communication not only helps convey information but also helps people assess risks, reduce panic, and guide community action. Several studies have shown that in disaster situations where there is adequate technical capability, communication failure can exacerbate the impact of the event that occurs (Seeger, 2006), (Jin., 2017). Therefore, communication should be considered an important part of disaster governance and not just a tool in crisis management. As Indonesia is a country with the third highest disaster risk conditions in the world according to the World Risk Report (WRR) 2023 (<https://www.tempo.co>), because geologically Indonesia is located at the meeting of four major plates namely Eurasia, Indo-Australia, Philippines, and Pacific (Natawidjaja, 2007), (Muhammad A, 2016), (Murtianto, 2016). As an archipelagic country located in the Pacific Ring of Fire (Annie Collopy, 2020), Indonesia has a very high level of vulnerability to various natural disasters, such as earthquakes, tsunamis, volcanic eruptions, floods, and landslides, so it is necessary to develop an effective and responsive disaster management system throughout the region.

Data from the National Disaster Management Agency (BNPB) indicates that from 2014 to 2023, there were 28,278 disasters, consisting of 8,179 floods, 7,258 landslides, 182 floods and landslides, 255 abrasion, 8,465 tornadoes, 383 droughts, 3,051 forest and land fires, 354 earthquakes, 9 tsunamis, 6 earthquakes and tsunamis, and 136 volcanic eruptions (<https://data.bnpb.go.id/>) across Indonesia.

Various efforts have been made to respond to these conditions, including the Indonesian government's comprehensive regulatory framework, Law Number 24 of 2007 concerning Disaster Management. However, empirically, this policy remains ineffective, particularly in terms of communicating risks to the public. The main problem lies not only in limited technology or resources, but

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also in communication systems that tend to be substandard. For example, in the 2018 Palu tsunami, the public lacked sufficient information and received unclear messages, resulting in insufficient time to evacuate (Titov, 2021). This phenomenon has also occurred in other incidents, where people were confused by erroneous and even conflicting information. This situation demonstrates the critical importance of communication in determining the effectiveness of a disaster response.

Therefore, the Crisis and Emergency Risk Communication (CERC) model offers a systematic framework for managing communications during disasters (Reynolds, 2005) and (Reynolds, 2002). In this model, the principles of empathy, speed (be first), accuracy (be right), and credibility (be credible) are crucial in conveying information. However, CERC studies have largely focused on developed countries with relatively high institutional capacity and public trust (Sellnow, 2014) and (Jin, 2017). In contrast, in developing countries like Indonesia, the effectiveness of crisis communication is influenced by people's trust in the government. In addition to information accuracy, message consistency, transparency, and public perception of institutional performance also significantly influence levels of public trust (Boin, 2024) and (Amriampa, 2025).

In disaster situations, communication has powerful social and cultural consequences. Local communities often trust information delivered by religious or traditional leaders more than official government sources (Aldrich, 2015). This situation demonstrates that effective communication requires consideration of the local context. This local context includes the language, principles, and belief systems that develop within the community (Nemakonde, 2024). Therefore, this research is interesting because previous studies have largely focused on the technical aspects of information delivery and have not comprehensively examined how such models can be applied in various social and institutional contexts. Therefore, there is a research gap in understanding how crisis communication can be developed more contextually in a developing country like Indonesia. Based on this phenomenon, this study aims to evaluate the use of CERC in disaster governance in Indonesia and identify various obstacles to its success. Furthermore, this study seeks to offer a more contextualized method by integrating the roles of local actors, the government, and the community in a more inclusive communication system. In this way, it is hoped that risk communication in Indonesia can be more effective in building public trust and increasing community resilience to disasters.

Contemporary disaster governance studies view risk communication as a crucial part of the governance process that determines the effectiveness of community response and resilience. It is no longer viewed solely as a technical tool. This theory aligns with the disaster leadership approach, which emphasizes the importance of coordination and authority sharing, as well as the relationship between the state and society when facing risks (Kapucu, 2011). In situations like this, communication is the primary means of linking policy to public action. Communication failures indicate not only poor information systems but also inconsistencies in institutional structures and power relations. Therefore, disaster communication analysis must be integrated into a broader governance framework rather than simply analyzing messages. One of the key concepts used as an analytical tool in this study is the Crisis and Emergency Risk Communication (CERC) model, developed by Barbara Reynolds. In this model, crisis communication must be conducted systematically through five stages: Pre-Crisis, Crisis Initial Stage, Crisis Period, Recovery, and Evaluation (Reynolds, 2005; Reynolds, 2002). The following diagram illustrates these stages:

Figure 1. Crisis and Emergency Risk Communication (CERC) Model

Source: (Reynolds, 2005)

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In this model, the nature of communication differs in each phase. However, in principle, fundamentals such as speed, accuracy, credibility, and empathy are generally emphasized in each phase. Communication in this context not only conveys information but also creates risk perceptions and influences public behavior in situations of uncertainty (Seeger, 2006). However, the CERC model is often assumed to operate within a context of strong institutional capacity, so its application in developing countries requires changes to be more adaptive and inclusive.

Furthermore, the level of public trust in the institutions that convey information significantly influences the effectiveness of crisis communication. Public trust is crucial in determining whether the message will be accepted or ignored by the public (Boin, 2024). This trust is built through consistent messaging, transparent information, and public impressions of government performance (Jin, 2017) (Boin, 2024). Public distrust in disaster situations can lead to rejection of evacuation instructions or other emergency policies. Therefore, legitimacy and accountability are crucial elements in crisis communication analysis.

In addition to institutional factors and trust, socio-cultural factors are also crucial in risk communication. The local knowledge approach emphasizes that communities possess adaptive knowledge systems and practices built on long-standing experience in dealing with disasters (Šakić Trogrlić, 2022). Many communities trust information delivered by local actors such as traditional leaders, religious figures, or community networks more than formal sources (Aldrich, 2015). This suggests that effective communication must combine top-down and bottom-up approaches. In other words, crisis communication must involve local actors as part of a broader communication system rather than relying solely on formal state structures.

On the other hand, technological advances have also transformed the way communities communicate in disaster situations. Digital platforms such as social media and early warning systems enable the rapid dissemination of information to large audiences. However, in reality, some communities do not enjoy these benefits equally. The ability to obtain and understand information depends heavily on digital literacy levels and access to technology. The digital divide remains a significant problem, according to numerous studies. This is especially true for vulnerable groups who have limited access to or use of technology (Erokhin, 2024), (Ginzarly, 2025), (Rizal E, 2025). Therefore, communication methods that rely solely on digital technology have the potential to isolate certain groups from information. This highlights the importance of using multi-channel methods that combine traditional and modern media. This study develops an analytical framework that combines three main dimensions: first, institutions through the CERC approach; second, public trust as a mediating factor; and third, technology and socio-cultural dimensions as the implementation context. By integrating these three dimensions, a more comprehensive analysis of crisis communication practices in Indonesia can be conducted. Therefore, this study not only assesses the relevance of the CERC model but also explores how the concept can be adapted to the context of developing countries. It is possible that this method will provide a theoretical contribution to developing a crisis communication model that is more contextual, inclusive, and responsive to the complexities of disaster governance.

2. METHODOLOGY

This study uses a qualitative method with a literature review approach, aiming to deeply understand the concepts and practices of crisis communication in disaster management. Leading international journals, official agency reports (BNPB, UNDRR), policy documents, and scientific publications on Crisis and Disaster Risk Communication (CERC) are secondary data sources used in this study. Various research findings are studied, compared, and analyzed. The goal is to identify patterns, differences, and challenges in implementing crisis communication, especially in developing countries like Indonesia. The CERC model is used as a basis for analysis and is then enriched with perspectives on technology, socio-cultural issues, public trust, and disaster management.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Crisis management in the event of natural disasters in Indonesia requires a comprehensive and organized approach that relies not only on rapid response to disasters but also focuses on pre-disaster risk reduction and long-term community capacity building. One highly relevant and applicable theory in this context is Crisis and Emergency Risk Communication (CERC), which consists of the Pre-Crisis Stage, Initial Event Stage, Maintenance Stage, Resolution and Recovery Stage, and Evaluation Stage (Reynolds, 2002) (Reynolds, 2005). This theory highlights the importance of appropriate, accurate, and empathetic risk communication at every stage of a crisis. Furthermore, adaptive community-based strategies and collaboration between various actors are also crucial elements in building robust crisis management in vulnerable areas in Indonesia. 3.1 Pre-Crisis Phase

One of the important stages before a crisis occurs is the period before a disaster occurs, when a disaster has not yet occurred, but there is a high level of risk and vulnerability. At this stage, the primary focus is on creating community preparedness, building trust in authorities, and mitigating the potential impact if a crisis does occur (Reynolds, 2002) (Reynolds, 2005). In Indonesia, the implementation of the CERC model in the pre-crisis phase can be seen in various disaster-related communications conducted by government agencies such as the National Disaster Management Agency (BNPB), the Meteorology, Climatology, and Geophysics Agency (BMKG), and other community groups. This stage consists of three essential elements according to CERC: (1) Risk Message Development, (2) Spokesperson Preparation, and (3) Partnership Development (Reynolds, 2002; Reynolds, 2005). All of

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these elements are closely related to the disaster context in Indonesia, which is geographically located on the Ring of Fire and prone to earthquakes, volcanic eruptions, floods, and tsunamis (Komang, 2022).

First, in terms of risk message development, the government, through the National Disaster Management Agency (BNPB), routinely provides information on potential disaster risks through various media. For example, the "SiapUntukSelamat" campaign is part of the government's public education efforts on how to protect oneself during an earthquake (<https://kotimkab.go.id/asal-hari-kesiapsiagaan-bencana/>). Furthermore, BNPB also launched the InaRisk portal, a digital platform that provides the public with access to information about disaster risks in their area (<https://inarisk.bnpb.go.id/>). However, the challenge is that many regions have limited access to information, both due to geographic location and low levels of digital literacy. Therefore, risk messages must be conveyed not only through online media, but also through conventional media such as local radio, banners, and direct learning through integrated health posts (Posyandu) or community religious studies.

Second, spokesperson preparation and training are key elements in building public trust in the information disseminated. In the pre-crisis period, it is crucial for local and central governments to select spokespersons who can convey information clearly, consistently, and reliably. For example, in the context of the Mount Merapi eruption, the Geological Disaster Technology Research and Development Center (BPPTKG) has appointed a representative who regularly provides updates through social media and press releases (<https://geologi.esdm.go.id/bpptkg>). This step was taken to instill public trust and prevent panic caused by unclear information.

Third, partnership development is crucial in strengthening communication networks. The government needs to build collaborations with community groups or indigenous groups, community organizations, local media, and religious groups to effectively disseminate and convey information. For example, in a tsunami-prone area like Padang Pariaman Regency, West Sumatra, collaboration between the Regional Disaster Management Agency (BPBD) and educational institutions in conducting regular evacuation simulations (<https://sumbardaily.com/>) demonstrates the application of the CERC principle in building two-way interaction with the community. The implementation of school- or village-based disaster simulations and emergency response training demonstrates that risk communication involving community participation can significantly improve preparedness.

However, the challenge in implementing CERC in the pre-crisis phase is the lack of public trust in government information, stemming from past negative experiences, misaligned messages between agencies, and unclear information. This is evident in the handling of COVID-19 several years ago. The lack of synchronization of information issued by the central and regional governments, coupled with the lack of open and transparent publication of COVID-19 case data (<https://www.tempo.co>), has led to increasing public confusion and panic. Therefore, CERC training must be an integral part of the basic skills of every BPBD member and regional official who have the potential to act as the frontline in communication during crises. Overall, CERC implementation in the pre-crisis phase in Indonesia has begun, but is not yet evenly distributed. The next step needs to focus on strengthening communication systems across platforms, improving the capabilities of spokespersons, and involving more local stakeholders to build resilient and disaster-ready communities.

1.2 Initial Event Stage

The initial event stage is the most crucial stage in crisis management, particularly in disaster management in Indonesia. This stage occurs after a natural disaster, where the community directly experiences the impact. In this situation, protecting human life is crucial, as everything operates under highly uncertain conditions, under high pressure, and requires a swift, accurate, and organized response. Indonesia, as a country prone to disasters such as earthquakes, tsunamis, floods, and volcanic eruptions, has frequently faced this stage. For example, during the earthquake and tsunami in Palu in 2018 or the earthquake in Cianjur in 2022, thousands of homes were quickly destroyed, many people died and were injured, infrastructure was damaged, and the community was trapped in a state of panic and chaos.

Therefore, the role of the National Disaster Management Agency (BNPB), Regional Disaster Management Agencies (BPBD), the Indonesian National Armed Forces (TNI)/Indonesian National Police (Polri), and humanitarian volunteers is crucial in this regard. After a disaster occurs, an emergency response command system is established, aid centers are established at the affected locations, and rescue and evacuation operations continue. One concrete example that can serve as a reference is the earthquake response in Cianjur. The local government, along with authorities, immediately evacuated victims from the rubble of buildings, opened roads blocked by landslides, and set up emergency tents and public kitchens for evacuees (<https://www.kompas.id>). Furthermore, institutions such as the Meteorology, Climatology, and Geophysics Agency (BMKG) actively provided the latest information on earthquake activity and the potential for aftershocks to address potential risks.

The Crisis and Emergency Risk Communication (CERC) theory is highly appropriate for describing communication strategies in crisis situations at this stage. CERC emphasizes the importance of communicating quickly (be first), accurately (be right), and with credibility (Reynolds, 2002) (Reynolds, 2005). Furthermore, communication needs to reflect empathy, convey respect, and encourage appropriate public action. At this stage, the public desperately needs clear guidance and reliable information to avoid becoming trapped in a dilemma. However, in reality, public confusion often persists regarding available information, both on social

media and in the news. This can exacerbate the situation and hinder the rescue process. Therefore, the presence of a spokesperson from an authorized agency to provide regular statements, both through print and digital media, is crucial.

Key challenges often encountered during this phase include damage to communication infrastructure, such as mobile phone signals and electricity, slow inter-agency coordination, a lack of accurate initial information on the number of victims and logistical needs, and uneven distribution of aid. To address these challenges, the government and humanitarian organizations have begun using technology such as drones for mapping disaster-affected areas, digital map-based logistics information systems, and community-driven reporting applications such as PetaBencana.id to expedite decision-making and information dissemination (<https://petabencana.id/map>). For example, in response to the eruption of Mount Semeru, the Center for Volcanology and Geological Hazard Mitigation (PVMBG) actively utilized volcanic activity monitoring technology to provide early warnings, while local volunteer networks were deployed to expedite the evacuation of communities in danger zones.

Equally important in this phase is the contribution of local communities. Many villages in Indonesia have initiated the Disaster Resilient Village (Destana) program, which has proven effective in responding quickly to disasters, especially before outside assistance arrives. Communities independently evacuate, provide first aid, and collectively record residents' needs. This collaboration between the government and local communities is a unique strength in accelerating recovery during critical moments. This approach demonstrates that successful disaster management depends not only on the strength of formal institutions but also on the independence of communities who have received prior training and knowledge

(<https://katalogkesiapsiagaan.bnppb.go.id/destana/>). Understanding the complexity and urgency of this phase, it is crucial for Indonesia to continue strengthening its overall crisis management capabilities through institutional strengthening, technology utilization, and increased community engagement. Regular assessments of the crisis response must also be conducted to ensure continuous improvement and greater preparedness in the future.

1.3 Maintenance Phase

The maintenance stage is a crucial phase in disaster management, where the focus shifts from saving lives to medium-term safety protection and basic recovery. During this phase, although conditions have begun to improve, various challenges remain. This phase lasts from several weeks to several months after a disaster, depending on the extent of the damage and the complexity of the affected area. Activities during this phase include logistical recovery, ongoing monitoring of potential lingering risks (such as aftershocks or subsequent flooding), ongoing aid distribution, healthcare services for injured and displaced persons, and maintaining effective communication with the community.

In the Indonesian context, this stage is often a critical moment where the resilience of the crisis management system is tested. For example, during the 2018 Lombok earthquake, although the initial evacuation process was swift, problems began to emerge during the maintenance phase. Thousands of residents living in evacuation tents faced various challenges related to health, lack of sanitation, and uneven distribution of logistics. <https://itb.ac.id/> The government, through the National Disaster Management Agency (BNPB) and the Ministry of Social Affairs, is working to ensure that basic needs such as food, clean water, health services, and temporary shelter remain available. However, inter-agency coordination is not yet fully efficient, and an inaccurate data collection system on victims has resulted in much aid being misdirected.

This phase also tests the effectiveness of communication during a crisis. Based on the Crisis and Emergency Risk Communication (CERC) model, communication strategies should focus on delivering integrated or continuous information, providing practical guidance, building trust, and ensuring the public remains calm but vigilant about developments. For example, during the Mount Merapi eruption, the government regularly provided updates on the status of volcanic activity through mass media and social media to encourage residents in vulnerable areas to not return home until the situation is declared safe. However, people often returned early due to a lack of understanding of the risks or a lack of communication.

Furthermore, a crucial aspect of the maintenance phase is physical and mental health support for disaster-affected communities. Various studies have shown that natural disasters not only leave physical scars but also cause lasting psychological trauma. In many disaster areas in Indonesia, psychosocial services remain weak during this phase. Systematic and sustainable mental health support programs are still limited, often occurring only as ad hoc activities by NGOs or volunteer groups (<https://daerah.sindonews.com>).

A good example of this phase can also be seen in the response to the floods in Jakarta in early 2020. The Jakarta Provincial Government, together with the Regional Disaster Management Agency (BPBD), the Health Office, and health volunteers, implemented a mobile post service that provided basic health services and distributed daily necessities to affected communities. This community-focused approach was a strength, streamlining logistical distribution and encouraging community participation in the rehabilitation of their surrounding environment (<https://pantaubanjir.jakarta.go.id/bencana-jakarta>). This strategy aligns with the community-based disaster management approach, which emphasizes the need for active community participation in every stage of disaster management, including the recovery phase. Overall, this phase demonstrates the importance of collaboration between the government, non-governmental organizations, communities, and the private sector in ensuring the continuity of services and strengthening community resilience in the face of disasters.

1.4 Resolution and Recovery Phase

The resolution and recovery phase represents the final stage of the crisis and disaster management cycle. Its primary goal is to return communities to normal, as reflected in the concept of "build back better." This phase is the most complex in Indonesia, as it focuses not only on rebuilding infrastructure (physical structures) but also on improving the psychological well-being of affected communities, the economic and social well-being of those affected. Strategies at this stage are crucial for how well communities recover and prepare for future disasters.

One example of the various disasters that have occurred in Indonesia is the post-tsunami response in Aceh in 2004. The Indonesian government established the Aceh-Nias Rehabilitation and Reconstruction Agency (BRR) to coordinate various long-term recovery programs. In this case, recovery efforts included rebuilding damaged homes, repairing health and education facilities, restoring basic infrastructure such as roads and bridges, and empowering communities. Therefore, the government's next steps will focus on collaboration and cooperation involving the community, the private sector, and other community institutions or non-governmental organizations. (<https://bencanapedia.id/BRR>). However, not all recovery conditions in Indonesia are running smoothly. For example, the recovery after the earthquakes in Lombok and Palu faced various obstacles such as slow disbursement of aid funds, lack of coordination between institutions, and difficult access to transportation (<https://www.tempo.co/>). In this case, both regional and central governments play a crucial role in establishing a roadmap for disaster management, so that post-disaster recovery can be implemented properly, and existing recovery policies can be more inclusive by considering vulnerable groups such as women, children, people with disabilities, and indigenous communities.

The Crisis and Emergency Risk Communication (CERC) model emphasizes the importance of public communication. The information provided needs to demonstrate the government's transparency in addressing issues, identifying emerging obstacles, and assuring the public that disaster recovery is underway. In some situations and circumstances, the government fails to provide fully transparent information, creating problems for community members. This situation was evident in the post-eruption recovery of Mount Sinabung, where displaced communities experienced prolonged housing uncertainty due to incomplete relocation policies (Rinaldy, 2018).

On the other hand, from a psychosocial (mental health) perspective, support groups involving religious and traditional leaders are crucial in helping residents overcome trauma and heal (<https://daerah.sindonews.com>). Furthermore, given Indonesia's diverse background, using an approach that respects local traditions is key to success at this stage. Improving the situation is not the end in itself, but rather the first step in preparing for much larger challenges in the future, as Indonesia is a country with a very high disaster risk. Therefore, every disaster experience must be used as momentum to strengthen a more resilient and equitable national disaster management system.

1.5 Evaluation Phase

The evaluation phase is a crucial stage in the crisis management process and is often overlooked in disaster management in Indonesia. However, this phase serves as a foundation for learning and future system development. The evaluation process aims to measure the effectiveness of the government's disaster response, including the efficiency of resource utilization, the appropriateness of existing policies, and the impact of mitigation on affected communities. Given Indonesia's geographic location in a high-risk disaster area, post-disaster evaluation must be a strategic step towards building a more responsive, adaptive, and sustainable disaster management system.

Therefore, in Indonesia, several key elements can be considered in this phase: analyzing interagency collaboration, the effectiveness of risk communication, the accuracy of logistics management and aid distribution, the speed of emergency response, and the appropriateness of recovery and rehabilitation programs to community needs. A concrete example can be seen in the evaluation of the 2018 earthquake and tsunami disaster in Palu. The report, compiled by the National Disaster Management Agency (BNPB) in collaboration with international partner agencies such as the UNDP and the IFRC, found significant challenges in coordination between central and regional agencies, particularly in the alignment of victim data and the management of logistics distribution. Furthermore, the tsunami early warning system proved ineffective, as many devices were not functioning when the event occurred, and information did not reach coastal communities quickly (<https://www.bmkg.go.id/>).

At this stage, a participatory approach is crucial for achieving a fair and reflective evaluation. The involvement of affected residents is necessary to identify challenges and gaps in the disaster management system. Evaluation methods that can be used include recipient satisfaction surveys, focus group discussions, logistics audits, and policy assessments conducted by unaffiliated institutions. Another example can be seen after the floods in Jakarta in 2020. Analysis by institutions such as the Indonesian Institute of Sciences (LIPI) highlighted the city's weak drainage system, uncertainty in spatial planning law enforcement, and a lack of disaster education for communities living in densely populated areas (<https://kumparan.com>).

Crisis communication models such as CERC emphasize the crucial aspect of the evaluation phase. Following a crisis, the government or relevant institutions must provide follow-up information to the public regarding the actions taken, what worked, what didn't work as expected, and what corrective measures will be taken. This is crucial for building public trust and encouraging

more active participation in the future. Unfortunately, in Indonesia, transparency in the evaluation process is often inadequate and not systematically recorded, preventing lessons learned from one disaster from being effectively applied to subsequent disasters. Furthermore, this evaluation phase also serves as a basis for revising disaster management policies, ensuring that future disaster management is more responsive and sustainable.

In international practice, many countries use after-action reviews (AARs) as the official evaluation mechanism, conducted immediately after a disaster response. Indonesia has begun implementing this approach in some cases, but it has not yet become a national standard (Annie Collopy, 2020). Therefore, strengthening evaluation capacity, training independent evaluators, and establishing an integrated disaster evaluation management information system are urgently needed. This ensures that evaluation is not merely an administrative activity but a key pillar of institutional learning in building national disaster resilience. Therefore, the evaluation phase is crucial for determining the extent to which Indonesia can learn from each crisis. With comprehensive, transparent, and participatory evaluations, the government can not only address weaknesses in previous disaster responses but also strengthen future public protection systems. Achieving this requires political commitment, data-driven planning, and the active involvement of all elements of the nation.

4. CONCLUSION

This research demonstrates that crisis communication, beyond being a supporting tool, is crucial for successful disaster management. The Crisis and Disaster Risk Communication (CERC) Model offers a clear framework for how communication should be conducted at each stage of a disaster. Due to numerous structural and contextual barriers in Indonesia, the implementation of this model has not been fully effective. Public confusion is often caused by a lack of inter-agency coordination, inconsistent messaging, and information delays. Conversely, public distrust of the government increases the likelihood of communication failures, resulting in the public not always following the information provided. Furthermore, this research shows that crisis communication requires a socio-cultural context and communication infrastructure. A top-down communication approach is ineffective because Indonesia's diverse society tends to trust local actors such as religious and traditional leaders more. Not all communities receive information equally due to limited access to digital technology. Therefore, a more adaptive communication approach is needed, one that combines the roles of local actors, the community, and the government within an integrated system. Therefore, future crisis communication will not only help convey information but also build trust and strengthen community resilience in the face of disasters.

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